

REVIEW ON MICROENCAPSULATION***Dr. Ambili M. V.**

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INTRODUCTION

Microencapsulation is a rapidly expanding technology.^[1] It is the process of applying relatively thin coatings to small particles of solids or droplets of liquids and dispersions. It provides the means of converting liquids to solids, of altering colloidal and surface properties, of providing environmental protection and of controlling the release characteristics or availability of coated materials. Microencapsulation is receiving considerable attention fundamentally, developmentally and commercially.

The term microcapsule is defined as a spherical particle with size varying from 50nm to 2mm, containing a core substance. Microspheres are in strict sense, spherical empty particles.^[2] However the terms microcapsule and microsphere are often used synonymously. The microspheres are characteristically

free flowing powders consisting of proteins or synthetic polymers, which are biodegradable in nature, and ideally having a particle size less than 200µm. Solid biodegradable microcapsules incorporating a drug dispersed or dissolved throughout the particle matrix have the potential for the controlled release of drug. These carries received much attention not only for prolonged release but also for the targeting of the anticancer drug to the tumors.

The concept of microencapsulation was initially utilized in carbonless copy papers. More recently it has received increasing attention in pharmaceutical and biomedical applications. Of the different dosage forms reported, nanoparticles and microparticles attained much importance, due to a tendency to accumulate in inflamed areas of the body. Nano and

microparticles for their attractive properties occupy unique position in drug delivery technology.

In a relatively simple form, a microcapsule is a small sphere with a uniform wall around it. The material inside the microcapsule is referred to as the core, internal phase, or fill, whereas the wall is sometimes called a shell, coating, or membrane. Some materials like lipids and polymers, such as alginate, may be used as a mixture to trap the material of interest inside. Most microcapsules have pores with diameters between a few micrometers and a few millimeters.

REASONS FOR ENCAPSULATION^[3-4]

The primary reason for microencapsulation is found to be either for sustained or prolonged drug release. This technique has been widely used for masking taste and odor of many drugs to improve patient compliance. This technique can be used for converting liquid drugs in a free flowing powder. The drugs, which are sensitive to oxygen, moisture or light, can be stabilized by microencapsulation. Incompatibility among the drugs can be prevented by microencapsulation. Vaporization of many volatile drugs e.g. methyl salicylate and peppermint oil can be prevented by microencapsulation. Many drugs have been microencapsulated to reduce toxicity and GI irritation including ferrous sulphate and KCl. Alteration in site of absorption can also be achieved by microencapsulation. Toxic chemicals such as insecticides may be microencapsulated to reduce the possibility of sensitization of factorial person. Bakan and Anderson reported that microencapsulated vitamin A palmitate had enhanced stability.

CLASSIFICATION^[5]

Microcapsules can be classified on three basic categories according to their morphology as follows,

1. Mononuclear
2. Polynuclear and
3. Matrix types

Mononuclear (core-shell) microcapsules contain the shell around the core, while polynuclear capsules have many cores enclosed within the shell. In matrix encapsulation, the core material is distributed homogeneously into the shell material. In addition to these three basic

morphologies, microcapsules can also be mononuclear with multiple shells, or they may form clusters of microcapsules

Microparticles offer various significant advantages as drug delivery systems, including^[1]

1. An effective protection of the encapsulated active agent against (e.g. enzymatic) degradation
2. The possibility to accurately control the release rate of the incorporated drug over periods of hours to months.
3. An easy administration (compared to alternative parenteral controlled release dosage forms, such as macro-sized implants).
4. Desired, pre-programmed drug release profiles can be provided which match the therapeutic needs of the patient.

Microparticulate drug delivery systems are an interesting and promising option when developing an oral controlled release system. Microcapsules are finally dispersed in various dosage forms, such as hard gelatin capsules, which may be enteric coated, soft gelatin capsules, or suspensions in liquids, all of which allow dispersion of individual microcapsules on release. Microcapsules continue to be of much interest in controlled release because of relative ease in design and formulation and partly on the advantages of microparticulate delivery systems. The latter include sustained release from each individual microcapsule and offer greater uniformity and reproducibility. Additional advantage over monolithic systems containing multiple doses is the greater safety factor in case of a burst or defective individual in subdivided dosage forms. Finally, it has been argued that multiple particle systems are distributed over a great length of gastro-intestinal tract, which should result in, (a) lowered local concentrations and hence reduced toxicity or irritancy, and (b) reduced variability in transit time and absorption rate.

BASIC CONSIDERATION OF MICROENCAPSULATION TECHNIQUE^[4-6]

Microencapsulation often involves a basic understanding of the general properties of microcapsules, Such as the nature of the core and coating materials, the stability and release characteristics of the coated materials and the microencapsulation methods. The intended physical characters of the encapsulated product and the intended use of the final product must also be considered.

- a. Core material:** The core material, defined as the specific material to be coated, can be liquid or solid in nature. The composition of the core material can be varied as the liquid core can include dispersed and/or dissolved material. The solid core can be a mixture of active constituents, stabilizers, diluents, excipients and release rate retardants or accelerators.
- b. Coating materials:** The coating material should be capable of forming a film that is cohesive with the core materials, be chemically compatible and non reactive with the core material and provide the desired coating properties such as strength, flexibility impermeability, optical properties and stability. The total thickness of the coatings achieved with microencapsulation techniques is microscopic in size.
- c. Stability, release and other properties:** Three important areas of current microencapsulation application are the stabilization of core materials, the control of the release or availability of core materials and separation of chemically reactive ingredients within a tablet or powder mixture. A wide variety of mechanisms is available to release encapsulated core materials; such as disruption of the coating can occur by pressure, shear or abrasion forces, permeability changes brought about enzymatically etc., improved gastro tolerability of drugs can be obtained by microencapsulation.
- d. Physical character of the final product:** Microcapsules should have desirable physical properties like ability to flow, to be compacted or to be suspended and the capsule wall must be capable of resisting the pressure during compression etc.
- e. coating materials:** A number of different substances both biodegradable as well as non-biodegradable have been investigated for the preparation of microcapsules. These materials include the polymers of natural and synthetic origin and also modified natural substances.

Examples of some microencapsulated drugs are^[7]

Sl no	Drug	Purpose	Product
1	Acetaminophen	Taste masking	Purpose
2	Aspirin	Taste masking, sustained release, reduce gastric irritation & incompatibilities	Tablets & capsule
3	Isosorbidi	Sustained release	Capsule

	nitrate		
4	Menthol	Reduction of volatility	Lotion
5	Progesterone	Sustained release	Varied
6	Potassium chloride	Reduced gastric irritation	Capsule
7	Vitamin A palmitate	Stabilization to oxidation	Dry powder

Some of the polymers used in the preparation of the microcapsules are classified and listed below^[5]

TECHNIQUES TO MANUFACTURE MICROCAPSULES^[8-9]

1. PHYSICAL METHODS

A. Air-suspension coating

Air-suspension coating, first described by Professor Dale Erwin wurster at the University of Wisconsin in 1959, gives improved control and flexibility compared to pan coating. In this process the particulate core material, which is solid, is dispersed into the supporting air stream and these suspended particles are coated with polymers in a volatile solvent leaving a very thin layer of polymer on them. This process is repeated several hundred times until the

required parameters such as coating thickness, etc., are achieved. The air stream which supports the particles also helps to dry them, and the rate of drying is directly proportional to the temperature of the air stream which can be modified to further affect the properties of the coating.^[8]

The re-circulation of the particles in the coating zone portion is effected by the design of the chamber and its operating parameters. The coating chamber is arranged such that the particles pass upwards through the coating zone, then disperse into slower moving air and sink back to the base of the coating chamber, making repeated passes through the coating zone until the desired thickness of coating is achieved.

B. Centrifugal extrusion

Liquids are encapsulated using a rotating extrusion head containing concentric nozzles. In this process, a jet of core liquid is surrounded by a sheath of wall solution or melt. As the jet moves through the air it breaks, owing to Rayleigh instability, into droplets of core, each coated with the wall solution.

While the droplets are in flight, the molten wall may be hardened or a solvent may be evaporated from the wall solution. Since most of the droplets are within $\pm 10\%$ of the mean diameter, they land in a narrow ring around the spray nozzle. Hence, if needed, the capsules can be hardened after formation by catching them in a ring-shaped hardening bath.

This process is excellent for forming particles 400–2,000 μm (16–79 mils) in diameter. Since the drops are formed by the breakup of a liquid jet, the process is only suitable for liquid or slurries. A high production rate can be achieved, up to 22.5 kg (50 lb) of microcapsules can be produced per nozzle per hour.^[9] Heads containing 16 nozzles are available.

C. Pan coating

The pan coating process, widely used in the pharmaceutical industry, is among the oldest industrial procedures for forming small, coated particles or tablets. The particles are tumbled in a pan or other device while the coating material is applied slowly.

Figure Pan coater

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D. Vibrational nozzle

Core-shell encapsulation or microgranulation (matrix-encapsulation) can be done using a laminar flow through a nozzle and an additional vibration of the nozzle or the liquid. The vibration has to be done in resonance with the Rayleigh instability and leads to very uniform droplets. The liquid can consist of any liquids with limited viscosities (0–10,000 mPa·s have

been shown to work), e.g. solutions, emulsions, suspensions, melts etc. The solidification can be done according to the used gelation system with an internal gelation (e.g. sol-gel processing, melt) or an external (additional binder system, e.g. in a slurry). The process works very well for generating droplets between 20–10,000 μm (0.79–393.70 mils), applications for smaller and larger droplets are known. The units are deployed in industries and research mostly with capacities of 1–20,000 kg per hour (2–44,000 lb/h) at working temperatures of 20–1,500 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ (68–2,732 $^{\circ}\text{F}$) (room temperature up to molten silicon). Heads are available with from one up to several hundred thousand nozzles.

E. Spray-drying

Spray drying serves as a microencapsulation technique when an active material is dissolved or suspended in a melt or polymer solution and becomes trapped in the dried particle. The main advantages are the ability to handle labile materials because of the short contact time in the dryer and the operation is economical.^[9] In modern spray dryers the viscosity of the solutions to be sprayed can be as high as 300 mPa·s. Applying this technique, along with the use of supercritical carbon dioxide, sensitive materials like proteins can be encapsulated.

2. PHYSICO-CHEMICAL METHODS

A. Ionotropic gelation

Ionotropic gelation occurs when units of uric acid in the chains of the polymer alginate, crosslink with multivalent cations. These may include calcium, zinc, iron and aluminium.

B. Coacervation-phase separation

Coacervation-phase separation consists of three steps carried out under continuous agitation.

1. Formation of three immiscible chemical phases: liquid manufacturing vehicle phase, core material phase and coating material phase.
2. Deposition of coating: core material is dispersed in the coating polymer solution. Coating polymer material coated around core. Deposition of liquid polymer coating around core by polymer adsorbed at the interface formed between core material and vehicle phase.
3. Rigidization of coating: coating material is immiscible in vehicle phase and is made rigid. This is done by thermal, cross-linking, or dissolution techniques.^[10]

Schematic representation of the coacervation process

- (a) Core material dispersion in solution of shell polymer;
- (b) separation of coacervate from solution;
- (c) coating of core material by microdroplets of coacervate;
- (d) coalescence of coacervate to form continuous shell around core particles.

3. CHEMICAL METHODS

A. Interfacial polycondensation

In interfacial polycondensation, the two reactants in a polycondensation meet at an interface and react rapidly. The basis of this method is the classical Schotten-Baumann reaction between an acid chloride and a compound containing an active hydrogen atom, such as an amine or alcohol, polyesters, polyurea, polyurethane. Under the right conditions, thin flexible walls form rapidly at the interface. A solution of the pesticide and a diacid chloride are emulsified in water and an aqueous solution containing an amine and a polyfunctional isocyanate is added. Base is present to neutralize the acid formed during the reaction. Condensed polymer walls form instantaneously at the interface of the emulsion droplets.^[14]

B. Interfacial cross-linking

Interfacial cross-linking is derived from interfacial polycondensation, and was developed to avoid the use of toxic diamines, for pharmaceutical or cosmetic applications. In this method, the small bifunctional monomer containing active hydrogen atoms is replaced by a biosourced polymer, like a protein. When the reaction is performed at the interface of an emulsion, the acid chloride reacts with the various functional groups of the protein, leading to the formation of a membrane. The method is very versatile, and the properties of the microcapsules (size, porosity, degradability, mechanical resistance). Flow of artificial microcapsules in microfluidic channels.

C. In-situ polymerization

In a few microencapsulation processes, the direct polymerization of a single monomer is carried out on the particle surface. In one process, e.g. cellulose fibers are encapsulated in polyethylene while immersed in dry toluene. Usual deposition rates are about 0.5 $\mu\text{m}/\text{min}$. Coating thickness ranges 0.2–75 μm (0.0079–2.9528 mils). The coating is uniform, even over sharp projections. Protein microcapsules are biocompatible and biodegradable, and the presence of the protein backbone renders the membrane more resistant and elastic than those obtained by interfacial polycondensation.

D. Matrix polymerization

In a number of processes, a core material is imbedded in a polymeric matrix during formation of the particles. A simple method of this type is spray-drying, in which the particle is formed by evaporation of the solvent from the matrix material. However, the solidification of the matrix also can be caused by a chemical change.

MECHANISM AND KINETICS OF DRUG RELEASE^[4]

Major mechanisms of drug release from microcapsules include diffusion, dissolution, osmosis and erosion.

Diffusion^[10]

Diffusion is the most commonly involved mechanism wherein the dissolution fluid penetrates the shell, dissolves the core and leak out through the interstitial channels or pores. Thus, the overall release depends on, (a) the rate at which dissolution fluid penetrates the wall of microcapsules, (b) the rate at which drug dissolves in the dissolution fluid, and (c) the rate at which the dissolved drug leak out and disperse from the surface. The kinetics of such drug release obeys Higuchi's equation as below:

$$Q = [D/J(2A-\epsilon CS)CSt]^{1/2}$$

Q : is the amount of drug released per unit area of exposed surface in time t;

D : is the diffusion coefficient of the solute in the solution;

A : is the total amount of drug per unit volume;

C_S : is the solubility of drug in permeating dissolution fluid;

ε : is the porosity of the wall of microcapsule;

J : is the tortuosity of the capillary system in the wall.

The above equation can be simplified to $Q = vt$ where, v is the apparent release rate.

Dissolution

Dissolution rate of polymer coat determines the release rate of drug from the microcapsule when the coat is soluble in the dissolution fluid. Thickness of coat and its solubility in the dissolution fluid influence the release rate.^[10]

Osmosis

The polymer coat of microcapsule acts as semi permeable membrane and allows the creation of an osmotic pressure difference between the inside and the outside of the microcapsule and drives drug solution out of the microcapsule through small pores in the coat.

Erosion

Erosion of coat due to pH and/or enzymatic hydrolysis causes drug release with certain coat materials like glyceryl monostearate, bee's wax and stearyl alcohol.

Attempts to model drug release from microcapsules have become complicated due to great diversity in physical forms of microcapsules with regard to size, shape and arrangement of the core and coat materials. The physiochemical properties of core materials such as solubility, diffusibility and partition coefficient, and of coating materials such as variable

thickness, porosity, and inertness also makes modeling of drug release difficult. However, based on various studies concerning the release characteristics, the following generalizations can be made:

1. Drug release rate from microcapsules conforming to reservoir type is of zero order.
2. Microcapsules of monolithic type and containing dissolved drug have release rates that are $t_{1/2}$ dependant for the first half of the total drug release and thereafter decline exponentially.
3. However, if a monolithic microcapsule containing large excess of dissolved drug, the release rate is essentially $t_{1/2}$ dependant throughout almost the entire drug release.

In monolithic capsules the path traveled by drug is not constant; the drug at the center travels a large distance than the drug at the surface. Therefore, the release rate generally decreases with time.^[10]

EVALUATION^[1]

a) Particle size and shape

The most widely used procedure to visualize microcapsule is conventional light microscopy, and scanning electron microscopy (SEM). Both techniques can be used to determine the shape and outer structure of microcapsule. SEM provides higher resolution in contrast to the light microscopy. It allows investigation of the microsphere surfaces and after particles are cross sectioned, it can also be used for the investigation of double walled systems. Confocal laser scanning microscopy (CLSM) is applied as a nondestructive visualization technique, which allows characterization of structures not only on surface, but also inside particle.

2. Fourier Trans form –infrared spectroscopy: (FTIR)

FTIR is used to determine the degradation of the polymeric matrix of the carrier system, and also interaction between drug and polymer system if present.

3. Density determination

The density of the microcapsule can be measured by using a multi volume pycnometer. Accurately weighed sample in a cup is placed in pycnomete, helium is introduced at a constant pressure in chamber and allowed to expand. The expansion results in a decrease in pressure within the chamber. From two pressure readings the volume and hence density of microcapsule can be determined.

4. Isoelectric point

The micro electrophoresis is an apparatus used to measure electrophoretic mobility of microsphere from which the isoelectric point can be determined. The electrophoretic mobility can be related to surface contained charge, ionisable behavior or ion absorption nature of microsphere.

5. Capture efficiency

The capture efficiency of microcapsule or the percent drug entrapment can be determined by allowing washed microcapsule to lyse. The lysate is then subjected to determination of active constituents as per monograph. The percent encapsulation efficiency is calculated using following equation.

$$\% \text{ Entrapment} = \frac{\text{Actual content}}{\text{Theoretical content}} \times 100$$

6. Contact angle

The angle of contact is measured to determine the wetting property of microcapsule. It determines the nature of microsphere in terms of hydrophilicity or hydrophobicity. The angle of contact is measured at the solid/air/water surface by placing a droplet in circular cell mounted above the objective of inverted microscope. Contact angle is measured at 20°C within a minute of decomposition of microsphere.

7. In-vitro release studies

Release studies for microcapsules can be carried out in different pH condition like pH 1.2 and pH 7.4 using USP rotating basket or paddle apparatus. The samples are taken at specific time intervals and are replaced by same amount of fresh medium. The samples withdrawn are analyzed as per the monograph requirement and release profile is determined using the plot of amount released a function of time.^[1]

Applications of microcapsules and microspheres^[5]

1. Prolonged release dosage forms. The microencapsulated drug can be administered, as microencapsulation is perhaps most useful for the preparation of tablets, capsules or parenteral dosage forms.
2. Microencapsulation can be used to prepare enteric-coated dosage forms, so that the medicament will be selectively absorbed in the intestine rather than the stomach.
3. It can be used to mask the taste of bitter drugs.

4. From the mechanical point of view, microencapsulation has been used to aid in the addition of oily medicines to tableted dosage forms. This has been used to overcome problems inherent in producing tablets from otherwise tacky granulations and in direct compression to tablets.
5. It has been used to protect drugs from environmental hazards such as humidity, light, oxygen or heat. Microencapsulation does not yet provide a perfect barrier for materials, which degrade in the presence of oxygen, moisture or heat, however a great degree of protection against these elements can be provided.
6. The separations of incompatible substances, for example, pharmaceutical eutectics have been achieved by encapsulation. This is a case where direct contact of materials brings about liquid formation. The stability enhancement of incompatible aspirin-chlorpheniramine maleate mixture was accomplished by micro-encapsulating both of them before mixing.
7. Microencapsulation can be used to decrease the volatility. An encapsulated volatile substance can be stored for longer times without substantial evaporation.
8. Microencapsulation has also been used to decrease potential danger of handling of toxic or noxious substances. The toxicity occurred due to handling of fumigants, herbicides, insecticides and pesticides have been advantageously decreased after microencapsulation.
9. The hygroscopic properties of many core materials may be reduced by microencapsulation.
10. Many drugs have been microencapsulated to reduce gastric irritation.
11. Microencapsulation method has also been proposed to prepare intrauterine contraceptive device.
12. In the fabrication of multilayered tablet formulations for controlled release of medicament contained in medial layers of tableted particles.

APPLICATIONS OF MICROENCAPSULATION IN DIFFERENT AREA^[15]

a) Agriculture^[16-20]

One of the most important applications of microencapsulated products is in the area of crop protection. Nowadays insect pheromones are becoming viable as a biorational alternative to conventional hard pesticides. Specifically, sex attractant pheromones can reduce insect populations by disrupting their mating process. Hence small amounts of species-specific pheromone are dispersed during the mating season, raising the background level of pheromone to the point where it hides the pheromone plume released by its female mate.

Polymer microcapsules, polyurea, gelatin and gum arabic serve as efficient delivery vehicles to deliver the pheromone by spraying the capsule dispersion. Further, encapsulation protects the pheromone from oxidation and light during storage and release.

b) Pharmaceutics^[21-23]

One of the major applications area of encapsulation technique is pharmaceutical/ biomedical for controlled/sustained drug delivery. Potential applications of this drug delivery system are replacement of therapeutic agents (not taken orally today like insulin), gene therapy and in use of vaccines for treating AIDS, tumors, cancer and diabetes. Protein such as insulin, growth hormone, and erythropoietin (used to treat anemia) are example of drugs that would benefit from this new form of oral delivery. The delivery of corrective gene sequences in the form of plasmid DNA could provide convenient therapy for a number of genetic diseases such as cystic fibrosis and hemophilia.

The spheres are engineered to stick tightly to and even penetrate linings in the gastrointestinal track before transferring their contents over time into circulatory system. Based on this novel drug delivery technique, Lupin has already launched in the market worlds first Cephalexin (Ceff-ER) and Cefadroxil (Odoxil OD) antibiotic tablets for treatment of bacterial infections. Aspirin controlled release version ZORprin CR tablets are used for relieving arthritis symptoms. Quinidine gluconate CR tablets are used for treating and preventing abnormal heart rhythms. Niaspan CR tablet is used for improving cholesterol levels and thus reducing the risk for a heart attack. Glucotrol (Glipizide SR) is an anti diabetic medicine used to control high blood pressure.

c) Food Industry^[24-30]

Currently there is a trend towards a healthier way of living, which includes a growing awareness by consumers for what they eat and what benefits certain ingredients have in maintaining good health. Preventing illness by diet is a unique offering of innovative so called "functional foods", many of which are augmented with ingredients to promote health. However simply adding ingredients to food products to improve nutritional value can compromise their taste, colour, texture and aroma. Sometimes they slowly degrade and lose their activity, or become hazardous by oxidation reactions. Ingredients can also react with components present in the food system, which may limit bioavailability.

Microencapsulation is used to overcome all these challenges by providing viable texture blending, appealing aroma release, and taste, odour and color masking. The technology enables food companies to incorporate minerals, vitamins, flavors and essential oils. In addition, microencapsulation can simplify the food manufacturing process by converting liquids to solid powder, decreasing production costs by allowing batch processing using low cost, powder handling equipment. Microcapsules also help fragile and sensitive materials survive processing and packaging conditions and stabilize the shelf life of the active ingredient.

d) Energy Generation

Hollow plastic microspheres loaded with gaseous deuterium (a fusion fuel) are used to harness nuclear fusion for producing electrical energy. The capsules are multilayered. The inner layer, which compresses the fuel, is a polystyrene shell about 3 mm thick. Next is a layer of poly(vinyl alcohol) about 3 mm thick, that retards diffusion of deuterium out of the capsule. The outer layer (the ablator) is about 50 mm thick and consists of a highly crosslinked polymer made from 2-butene. During the fusion experiments, energy from high powered laser beams is absorbed by the surface of the microcapsule shell. As the outside of the shell (called ablator) burns off, the reaction force accelerates the rest of the shell inward, compressing and heating the deuterium inside. This results in high densities and temperature in the centre of the capsule leading to the fusion of deuterium nuclei to give tritium, helium and other particles releasing an enormous amount of energy. This process has been named as inertial confinement fusion (ICF). Such ICF targets made of organic microcapsules have been in use since 1980s.^[30]

e) Catalysis

Transition metal based catalytic processes are of vital importance to pharmaceutical, agrochemical and fine chemical industries. A vast proportion of such catalytic metal species are often expensive and toxic, thereby making operational handling potentially hazardous. Microencapsulation has recently been recognized as a useful alternative strategy to enable safe handling, easy recovery, reuse and disposal at an acceptable economic cost. Polyurea microcapsules due to their insolubility in aqueous and organic solvents, and resistance towards degradation have been used for encapsulation of different catalysts. Metal species such as palladium (II) acetate and osmium tetroxide have been encapsulated in polyurea microcapsules and used successfully as recoverable and reusable catalysts without significant

leaching and loss of activity. It is thought that the urea functionality, which forms the backbone of the polymer, ligates and retains the metal species within the polymeric matrix. Futuristic trend is towards incorporation of other chelating and ligating functional groups within the polyurea framework to study rate enhancement in such reactions, and trying other polymers for encapsulation.^[31,32]

Defence

One of the important defence applications of microencapsulation technology is in self-healing polymers and composites. They possess microencapsulated healing agents embedded within the matrix and offer tremendous potential for providing long-lived structural materials. The microcapsules in self-healing polymers not only store the healing agent during quiescent states, but provide a mechanical trigger for the self-healing process when damage occurs in self-healing polymers and composites. They possess microencapsulated healing agents embedded within the matrix and offer tremendous potential for providing long-lived structural materials. The microcapsules in self-healing polymers not only store the healing agent during quiescent states, but provide a mechanical trigger for the self-healing process when damage occurs in the host material and the capsules rupture.

The microcapsules possess sufficient strength to remain intact during processing of the host polymer, yet rupture when the polymer is damaged. High bond strength to the host polymer combined with a moderate strength microcapsule shell are required. To provide long shelf life the capsules must be impervious to leakage and diffusion of the encapsulated healing agent for considerable time. These combined characteristics are achieved with a system based on the in situ polymerization of urea-formaldehyde microcapsules encapsulating dicyclopentadiene healing agent. The addition of these microcapsules to an epoxy matrix also provides a unique toughening mechanism for the composite system. Such microcapsules have tremendous application in aerospace area for making self-repairable spacecrafts. Such self-healing spacecrafts open up the possibility of longer duration missions by increasing the lifetime of a spacecraft.

Microencapsulation is also used for designing special fabrics for military personnel, for their enhanced chemical protection against chemical warfare. For this purpose special reactive microcapsules have been developed which can be applied to fabrics or finished garments to provide reactive sites for neutralisation of chemical reagents. This involves microencapsulation of conventional decontamination chemicals that are currently effective

for deactivation of toxic mustard blistering agents (H agents) and toxic nerve agents known conventionally as G agents, for example isopropylmethyl phosphonofluoridate (GB, sarin) and the V agents, and formulation of the microcapsules in a resin finish that can be uniformly applied to fabric substrates. The preferred microcapsules containing a decontaminating agent were obtained by organic phase separation with ethyl cellulose microcapsules containing a solid decontamination agent consisting of sym-bis (N-chloro-2,4,6-trichlorophenyl) urea and ZnO. The microcapsules were then bonded to the fabric with an acrylic binder emulsion. The very thin walls (1 to 10 microns) of microcapsules allow for rapid agent permeation for optimum decontamination and thus protect the wearer from toxic chemical agent.^[33-39]

RECENT ADVANCES IN MICROENCAPSULATION

- The technique is usually applied for targeted drug delivery, protection of the molecule and stability of the core material. Microencapsulation system offers potential advantages over conventional drug delivery systems and also established as unique carrier systems for many pharmaceuticals. The microcapsules are widely applied in pharmaceutical for Novel Drug Delivery System (NDDS), latest formulations, delivery of DNA vaccines, pro drug approach, biodegradable and biocompatible material.

Other than pharmaceutical microcapsules are widely used in delivery of probiotic, pesticide industry, food technology, beverages and cell immobilization etc. Although significant advances have been made in the field of microencapsulation, still many challenges need to be rectified during the appropriate selection of core materials, coating materials and process techniques.^[40]

- Microencapsulation is one of the highly efficient methods. Many different active materials like drugs, pesticides, flavours, enzymes, vitamins and catalysts have been successfully encapsulated in microcapsules made from a variety of polymeric and non polymeric materials like poly(ethylene glycol), poly(methacrylate), poly(styrene), cellulose, poly(lactide), poly(lactide-co-glycolide), gelatin and acacia, etc. This technology has been used in many fields like pharmaceutical, agriculture, food, printing, cosmetic, textile and defence. In defence sector this technology has introduced the concept of self-healing composites as well as chemical decontaminating fabrics.^[1]
- A perfectly designed controlled drug delivery system can be of huge advantage towards solving problems concerning the targeting of drug to a specific organ or tissue and controlling the rate of drug delivery at the target site. Novel drug delivery systems have

various advantages over other conventional drug therapy. In which microencapsulation is one approach for achieving the novel drug delivery dosage forms such as sustained release and controlled release, though the development of oral controlled release systems has been a challenge to formulation scientist due to their inability to restrain and focus the system at targeted areas of gastrointestinal tract. Microparticulate drug delivery systems are an interesting and promising option when developing an oral controlled release system.^[5]

- The encapsulation efficiency of the microparticles or microsphere or microcapsule depends upon different factors like concentration of the polymer, solubility of polymer in solvent, rate of solvent removal, solubility of organic solvent in water etc. Microencapsulation is achieved by a myriad of techniques. Substances are microencapsulated with the intention that the core material be confined within capsule walls for a specific period of time. Alternatively, core materials may be encapsulated so that the core material will be released either gradually through the capsule walls, known as controlled release or diffusion, or when external conditions trigger the capsule walls to rupture, melt, or dissolve.^[6]
- Microencapsulation as a process of enclosing micron sized particles of solids or droplets of liquids or gasses in an inert shell, which in turn isolates and protects them from the external environment as well as control the drug release profile. Microencapsulated particle is having diameter between 3 [-] 800 μ m which differ them from other technologies such as nanotechnology and macroparticle in their morphology and internal structure.^[41]
- Microencapsulation is a well-established dedicated to the preparation, properties and uses of individually encapsulated novel small particles, as well as significant improvements to tried-and-tested techniques relevant to micro and nano particles and their use in a wide variety of industrial, engineering, pharmaceutical, biotechnology and research applications. Its scope extends beyond conventional microcapsules to all other small particulate systems such as self-assembling structures that involve preparative manipulation.^[4]
- 'Small is better' would be an appropriate motto for the many people studying microencapsulation. In its simplest form, a microcapsule is a small sphere with a uniform

wall around it. The reasons for microencapsulation are countless. Microencapsulation system offers potential advantages over conventional drug delivery systems and also established as unique carrier systems for many pharmaceuticals. Although significant advances have been made in the field of microencapsulation, still many challenges need to be rectified during the appropriate selection of core materials, coating materials and process techniques.^[3]

- In a relatively simplistic form, a microcapsule is a small sphere with a uniform wall around it. In some cases, the core must be isolated from its surroundings, as in isolating vitamins from the deteriorating effects of oxygen, retarding evaporation of a volatile core, improving the handling properties of a sticky material, or isolating a reactive core from chemical attack. In other cases, the objective is not to isolate the core completely but to control the rate at which it leaves the microcapsule, as in the controlled release of drugs or pesticides. The problem may be as simple as masking the taste or odor of the core, or as complex as increasing the selectivity of an adsorption or extraction process.^[3]
- Novel drug delivery systems have several advantages over conventional multi dose therapy. Much research effort in developing novel drug delivery system has been focused on controlled release and sustained release dosage forms. Now considerable efforts are being made to deliver the drug in such a manner so as to get optimum benefits. There are various approaches in delivering a therapeutic substance to the target site in a sustained controlled release fashion. One such approach is using microspheres as carriers for drugs. Microencapsulation is a process where by small discrete solid particles or small liquid droplets are surrounded and enclosed by an intact shell. Microencapsulation is used to modify and delayed drug release form pharmaceutical dosage forms. A well designed controlled drug delivery system can overcome some of the problems of conventional therapy and enhance the therapeutic efficacy of a particular drug. It is the reliable means to deliver the drug to the target site with specificity, if modified, and to maintain the desired concentration at the site of interest without untoward effects. Microspheres received much attention not only for prolonged release, but also for targeting of anticancer drugs to the tumor.^[7]
- An appropriately designed controlled release drug delivery system can be a major advance towards solving problems concerning to the targeting of drug to a specific organ or tissue and controlling the rate of drug delivery to the target site. The development of

oral controlled release systems has been a challenge to formulation scientist due to their inability to restrain and localize the system at targeted areas of gastrointestinal tract. Microparticulate drug delivery systems are an interesting and promising option when developing an oral controlled release system.^[10]

- A number of techniques have been developed for encapsulating small particles ranging in size from a few microns or less to about 2000 μ m. In addition, there are other factors which must be given careful consideration in the development of suitable microencapsulated products, such as: physical and chemical properties of the core material and wall material; post-treatment of capsules; interaction of capsules and substrate; storage conditions; release mechanisms; and economics.^[9]

CONCLUSION

Microfabricated system offers potential advantages over conventional drug delivery systems. Microspheres and microcapsules are established as unique carrier systems for many pharmaceuticals and can be tailored to adhere to targeted tissue systems. Hence, microcapsules and microspheres can be used not only for controlled release but also for targeted delivery of drugs to a specific site in the body. Although significant advances have been made in the field of microencapsulation, there are still many challenges ahead in this field. Of particular importance are the development of cheaper biopolymers for the microencapsulation technology and the development of universally acceptable evaluation methods especially for bioadhesive microspheres. Therefore, the development of safe and efficient particular systems will require, in the future, in depth investigations of both the biological and technological aspects of these systems.

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